

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF RENAL MORPHOLOGY IN ACUTE RADIATION

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Resume. With acute radiation, there is a violation of the structural elements of the kidney, pathological indicators characterizing the structural and functional state of nephrons. These values are most pronounced in 5- and 8-month-old rats, which distal convoluted tubules and their diameters are equal to the diameters of the control group.

Keywords. kidney, acute irradiation, rat, experiment.

In the world, there is an increase in morbidity associated with disorders of the functioning of the genitourinary system. The main reason for the increase in the number of diseases is environmental pollution and, as a result, a violation of the protective functions and adaptation reserves of the human body. Studying the structural and functional properties of the kidney is an urgent problem, since the kidneys, according to many researchers, have a more complex structure than other organs of the urinary system [2,4,6,8,10,12]. However, due to a lack of knowledge about the side effects of acute radiation exposure, many problems aimed at preventing diseases, early diagnosis and minimizing side effects of these factors remain unresolved [2,29,31,33]. Assessment of the morphofunctional status of the kidney in acute radiation sickness after prolonged exposure to ionizing radiation, comparison of the morphometric and morphological characteristics of these organs when using biostimulants with different periodicity and, thus, the development of an optimal algorithm for prevention, diagnosis and treatment are among the priority tasks that scientists face [1,6,8,10,12,34]. In our country, the country's health care system has undergone radical changes and a number of large-scale program works are underway. In this regard, a number of large-scale program measures have been carried out.

While positive results have been achieved in improving the quality of treatment of radiation-induced diseases of the reproductive system, in particular cancer, there is a need to develop new evidence-based therapies for those skilled in the art. Solving the set tasks will reduce morbidity and mortality as a result of complications of oncological diseases developing as a result of radiation, will increase the quality of modern medical services to a new level in the diagnosis

and treatment of diseases, as well as improve the use of modern technologies in the provision of high-quality medical services [1,3,5,7,9,11,24]. Currently, for the prevention and treatment of infectious, invasive, radiation diseases, in order to mobilize the natural defenses of the body and correct physiological and immunobiological reactions, the issue of the widespread use of biologically active substances is being updated. Biogenic stimulants, changing the activity of enzyme systems, increase the level of metabolic processes and the body's resistance to various pathogenic influences [26,28,30,32]. The high sensitivity of the kidney to the effects of factors of different genesis and the ability of one of the first in the body to respond with adaptive changes in cytoarchitectonics and morphological organization have been experimentally proven. Reactive morphofunctional shifts in the kidneys, observed when damaging factors affect the body, make it possible to determine the nature and intensity of the adaptive response of the kidney to this effect. Morphometric research methods that meet the modern requirements of evidence-based medicine allow an objective assessment of changes in the structural and functional state of the kidney [14,16,18,20,22,25,27]. A study of the available literature revealed a lack of information on the effect of acute radiation on the genitourinary system, namely kidney function. In addition, postnatal changes in morphometric parameters of kidney structure in chronic radiation disease and their correction using a biostimulator is an open question until today.

The purpose of the study. To study age-related changes in the morphofunctional properties of the kidneys and the effects of acute radiation. The object of the study was 198 white mongrel male rats of 3 days and 3, 6, 9, 12 months of age in the experimental research laboratory of the Bukhara State Medical Institute.

Research methods. At the beginning of the experiment, all sexually mature rats were quarantined for a week, and after the exclusion of somatic or infectious diseases, they were transferred to the usual vivarium regime. The animals were divided into 4 groups (n=143): group I – control (n=55); group II – rats exposed to radiation for 20 days from 2 months of age at a dose of 0.2 Gy (the total dose was 4.0 Gy) (n=59); Group III – rats who received radiation for 20 days from the age of 2 months at a dose of 0.2 Gy (the total dose was 4.0 Gy) and received the drug ASD - 2 in parallel during irradiation at a dose of 0.2 ml of pure ASD - 2 dissolved in 0.4 ml of distilled water (n=60); IV – a group of rats who received a course of irradiation for 20 days (from the age of 2 months at a dose of 0.2 Gy, where the total dose was 4.0 Gy) and after the end of irradiation received the drug ASD - 2 at a dose of 0.2 ml of pure ASD - 2 dissolved in 0.4 ml of distilled

water ($n = 57$). These dosages of ASD - 2 were calculated empirically and administered daily intragastrically with a metal probe in the form of a solution. In the visual evaluation of the external structure of the kidneys of rats after irradiation with the administration of pure ASD-2 fractions at a dose of 0.2 mL of the experimental group did not differ from those of the 1st and 2nd groups of animals.

At the same time absolute weight of kidneys varies from 933.72 mg to 1250.56 mg, in average - $1092,13 \pm 4,25$ mg, which is more in comparison with the 2nd group of experiment by 7.28%, length of right kidney from 15.49 mm to 17.43 mm, in average - $16,46 \pm 0,37$ mm, more in comparison with the 2nd group of experiment by 5.03%, width - from 7.79 mm to 10.18 mm, in average - $8,82 \pm 0,43$ mm, more in comparison with the 2nd group of the experiment by 4.19%, thickness - from 7.74 mm to 8.81 mm, in average - $8,27 \pm 0,63$ mm, more in comparison with the 2nd group of the experiment by 4.34%; the volume of the right kidney varies from 936.96 mm³ to 1563.22 mm³, in average - $1200,61 \pm 17,23$ mm³, more than the 2nd group of the experiment by 16.24%.

When comparing the obtained data with the parameters of rats after irradiation with 2 fractions in a dose of 0.2 ml of the experimental group, the absolute weight of the kidneys is 1.05%, the length of the right kidney is 3.07%, the width is 3.49%, the thickness is 1.96%, and the volume of the right kidney is 4.87% less than the first experimental group. After irradiation of 2 fractions at a dose of 0.2 mL of the experiment group, a positive effect on the histological structure of cortical nephrons in rats acted.

A histomorphometric study showed that after the end of exposure to rat conditions after irradiation of the 2 fraction in a dose of 0.2 ml of the experiment group, the total area of the renal bodies ranges from 2002.83 μm^2 to 2085.94 μm^2 , in the mean of $2043,93 \pm 16,34$ μm^2 , which is greater compared to the 2nd experiment group on the 5.00%. the area of the vascular glomerulus from 1680.91 μm^2 to 1735.59 μm^2 , in the average - $1720,12 \pm 43,37$ μm^2 , is 3.86% more compared to the 2nd group of the experiment, capsule lumen area is from 671.47 μm^2 to 781.20 μm^2 , mean - $740,64 \pm 37,18$ μm^2 . more than the 2nd group of the experiment by 6.97%.

When comparing the obtained data with the parameters of rats after irradiation of the 2 fraction in a dose of 0.2 ml of the experimental group, the total area of the renal bodies of the 2.13%, the area of the vascular glomerulus per 1.87%, and the area of the capsule lumen is 3.83% less than the 1st experimental group. In rats, after irradiation of 2 fractions in a dose of 0.2 ml of the

experimental group, the detected abnormalities were quickly restored to the rat body and the areas of the renal bodies and the lumen of the capsule remained more than the values of the 2nd group.

Conclusions. 1. With acute radiation, there is a violation of the structural elements of the kidney, pathological indicators characterizing the structural and functional state of nephrons. These values are most pronounced in 5- and 8-month-old rats, which distal convoluted tubules and their diameters are equal to the diameters of the control group.

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